

The Effect of Nutritional support on predetermined parameters in Patients with Chemo Radiation for Head and Neck CancersAsharani. Veerabhadhruni¹, K. Sudhakar², Subbarayudu³¹Junior Resident, Department of Radiation Oncology, NRI Medical College & General Hospital, Chinakakani – 522 503 Managalgi, Guntur (A.P.)²Associate Professor, Department of Radiation Oncology, NRI Medical College & General Hospital, Chinakakani – 522 503 Managalgi, Guntur (A.P.)³Medical Physicist, Department of Radiation Oncology, NRI Medical College & General Hospital, Chinakakani – 522 503 Managalgi, Guntur (A.P.)

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Abstract:**Background:** Head and neck cancer, the most common form of tumour in developing countries. For patients undergoing chemo-radiation for head and neck cancers, nutritional support is essential for minimizing side effects and enhancing treatment success. In contrast to home-based nutritional therapy, this study examines the impact of structured nutritional support on clinical and biochemical indicators.**Methodology:** Fifty patients with head and neck squamous cell carcinoma were included in an 18-month prospective observational research at NRI Medical College. Patients were randomized into two groups, with Group B receiving structured nutritional care and Group A receiving home-based nutritional support. Weight, haemoglobin, and albumin levels were among the clinical measurements, and treatment outcomes, side effects, infections, and re admissions to the hospital were assessed.**Results:** Structured nutritional support significantly reduced treatment interruptions ($p=0.0308$) and hospital re admissions ($p=0.0047$) compared to home-based care. Haemoglobin, albumin, and weight changes showed no statistically significant differences across groups (e.g., post-treatment haemoglobin $p=0.4786$). Group B patients tolerated treatment better, with fewer Grade 3 mucositis cases (4% vs 6%) and severe skin reactions (8% vs 4%). These findings underscore the importance of organized nutritional care during chemo radiation for improved outcomes.**Conclusion:** Patients receiving chemo-radiation therapy for head and neck cancers benefit from structured dietary support, which also lowers hospital re admissions and increases treatment adherence.**Keywords:** Head and Neck Cancer, Tumour, Chemo-Radiation, Nutritional Therapy.

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Introduction

Head and neck cancer, the most common form of tumour, ranking sixth in terms of incidence and eighth in terms of death as a leading cause of cancer worldwide, radiation therapy remains the best and most effective treatment thus far [1]. Often it is observed males are more prone to the disease and the incidence is higher among older individuals i.e. those who are more than 60 years old (Figure 1) [2]. Unfortunately, patients with head and neck cancers are increasingly becoming a malnourished population due to the effect of the tumour and the treatment for the same. The two primary causes of malnutrition are lack of nutrient intake or nutritional metabolism harm to the nutritional state of disorder

The main signs include edema, weight loss, or gradual emaciation. Serious cases of hypo-albumen can harm several organs. The risk of malnutrition to

a patient depends on the location, kind, and stage of the tumour. Up to 74.2% of patients with head-neck cancer suffer from malnutrition. The impact factors vary for malnourished patients, however, the main ones remain tumours brought on by metabolic irregularities in the body, adverse consequences from anticancer treatments, and tumour diagnoses related to psychological and social issues. [3].

Malnutrition occurs from the patients insufficient food intake [8]. As indicated by Ottery [9], around 20% of cancer patients died from the starvation effects as opposed to the tumour itself. American Society for Parenteral Enteral Nutrition and the French Cooperation Organization presented certain viewpoints on principles and practices regarding nutritional support based on the collection of prior findings from the assessment study. All

patients, especially those suffering from cancer would need a clarifying nutritional survey while on treatment. These important guidelines underscored the need for nutritional status assessment as soon as possible in routine evaluation. Moreover, dietary therapies must be initiated as early as possible for patients who require them. The nutrition intervention project should be incorporated into the comprehensive treatment plan [10].

Food-based therapies, the use of oral nutritional supplements, and snacking to augment meal intake are all examples of oral nutritional assistance [12]. The nutritional state can affect the recurrence of cancer after the disease has stabilized or gone into full

remission.[15]. Healthy status of diet is the criteria which has to have a significant impact on the well-being of the patient [16]. A reliable predictor of malnutrition, which is associated with hospitalization and treatment interruptions, is involuntary weight loss for head and neck cancer of more than 5% in a month, or more than 1% to 2% per week [21,22]. The present study aims to investigate the impact of nutritional supplementation on certain parameters of patients undergoing CRT for head and neck cancers. From these results we can draw a conclusion regarding dietary treatments clinical relevance in enhancing outcomes, improving patient care, and providing a better quality of life for this vulnerable population.

Methods

Study design: For two years, from August 2022 to December 2023 (18 months), a prospective observational study was carried out in a hospital for patients with head and neck cancer. Patients with head and neck cancer who met the inclusion and exclusion criteria and had biopsies were randomly assigned.

Sample size calculation: The formula for determining the required number of study participants is $N=4PQ/L2$, where P is the head and neck cancer prevalence, or roughly 10% at our institution; Q is 100-P, and the allowable error is 10%. This means that $n=4 \times 10 \times 90 / 100 = 36$. Fifty individuals were enrolled in the Department of Radiation Oncology at NRI Medical College with the intention of receiving final chemo radiation for head and neck squamous cell cancer. According to the randomization strategy created online, they were either provided structured nutritional care with or without enteral feeding, or they kept receiving nutritional support at home. For analysis purposes, the patients are divided into two groups (A and B) based on this. Group B participants got organized nutritional help, whereas Group A participants continued to receive home-based nutritional support.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients above 18 years of age.
- Patients receiving final chemoradiation therapy for head and neck cancer.
- Only home-based nutritional support was available; there was no prior nutritional help.
- Subjects providing informed consent

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients who did not provide informed consent
- Patients below 18 years of age
- Any nutritional assistance that already exists apart from home-based nutritional support.
- Any congenital metabolic disorders that need for extra dietary care.

Treatment planning: A thermoplastic cast (mold) was used to completely immobilize the patients while they were in a supine position with their heads resting. Depending on the disease characteristics at presentation, a daily dose of 1.8-2 Gy in 33-35 #s for five days a week for six to seven weeks total, which adds up to a dose of 66-70 Gy. Cisplatin administered weekly for four to six cycles at a dose determined by multiplying BSA by 40 mg/m². Patients who are contraindicated for cisplatin therapy are administered carboplatin weekly for 4-6 cycles at a dose determined using Calvert's formula, which equals an AUC 2 dose.

Nutritional support: The subjects in group A continued receiving nutritional support at home, with data gathered using the 24-hour recall approach. Patients in group B receive systematic dietary support based on a chart provided by a dietician, and their compliance is closely monitored. The picture below illustrates the diet chart's format.

Follow up: One month after treatment ended, all patients were checked in at the outpatient department. Patients' weight, hemoglobin level, albumin level, infections, and morbidity were evaluated. According to the data, each mortality that occurs is recorded upon telephone confirmation with the attendees. Patients were told to come in if they needed medical attention during treatment or after finishing it.

Statistical Analysis: Standard statistical software was used to analyze the data that was gathered (SPSS version 26.0). By using this tool, it was assessed data of patient's details, habits, BMI distribution, and clinical outcomes. P-values <0.05 were considered statistically significant. Weight, haemoglobin, and serum albumin changes were likened across time points and between groups to measure the nutritional effect, with follow-up comparisons revealing no significant differences.

Results

Table 1 lists the demographic details of two patient groups (A and B), each of which consists of 25

participants and totals 50 people. In both groups, the majority of patients are men rather than women. In all groups, the mean age was similar (A: 54.12 years, B: 53.76 years, total: 53.94 years). 17 patients (13 in A, 4 in B) had diabetes mellitus (DM), 8 patients (5 in A, 3 in B) had hypertension (HTN), and 5 patients (3 in A, 2 in B) had other diseases. 17 patients (13 in A, 4 in B) had diabetes mellitus (DM), 8 patients (5 in A, 3 in B) had hypertension (HTN), and 5 patients (3 in A, 2 in B) had hypertension (HTN), and 5 patients

(3 in A, 2 in B) had other diseases. Group A had a higher prevalence of smoking, chewing tobacco, and drinking alcohol: 26 smokers (16 in A, 10 in B), 10 tobacco users (6 in A, 4 in B), and 15 alcohol users (12 in A, 3 in B). Four individuals had low BMI (1 in A, 3 in B), twenty had normal BMI (13 in A, 7 in B), and twenty-six had high BMI (11 in A, 15 in B), according to the BMI distribution. Five patients showed signs of pallor.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of patients

Sl. No.	Characteristic	A Group	B Group	Total
1.	No. of Subjects	25	25	50
2.	Sex	Male	15	38
		Female	2	10
3.	Mean Age	54.12	53.76	53.94
4.	Co-morbidities	DM	4	17
		HTN	3	8
		Others	2	5
5.	Habits	Smoking	10	26
		Tobacco chewing	4	10
		Alcohol	3	15
6.	BMI	Low	3	4
		Normal	7	20
		High	15	26
7.	Pallor	3	2	5

The study shows that the hypopharynx was the most common malignancy site (15 cases, 30%), followed by the oral cavity (14 cases, 28%) and oropharynx (11 cases, 22%). Less frequent sites included the larynx (6 cases, 12%) and nasopharynx (3 cases, 6%). Group A showed higher oral cavity cancer cases (18%), whereas Group B had more

hypopharyngeal cases (20%). Clinically, Stage IVA dominated with 68% of cases (38% in Group A, 30% in Group B). Stage III accounted for 16% (4% in Group A, 12% in Group B), Stage II for 8% (2% Group A, 6% Group B), and Stage I for 6%. These findings indicate late-stage diagnoses in most cases.

Figure 4: Frequency of adverse reactions (dysphagia, mucositis, and skin reactions) in both the groups

Figure 7: Comparison of post treatment events in both the groups

Discussion

Our study shows that out of the 25 participants in the B Group of our study, 15 (30%) needed an NG tube inserted because they were having trouble swallowing or were experiencing pain, or both. The remaining 10 patients (20%) just received a diet chart depending on their nutritional needs; they did not receive any NG tubes. Nine (18%) of the patients who needed an NG tube placed needed it before treatment began, while six (12%) needed it while receiving treatment.

In Group A, with home-based nutritional support, the mean haemoglobin level decreased from 12.46 pre-treatment to 11.65 post-treatment and 11.62 at follow-up in Figure 6. In Group B, receiving structured nutritional support, mean haemoglobin decreased from 12.07 to 11.99 post-treatment and 11.91 at follow-up. Of the 22 patients who experienced treatment disruptions, 16 were in the A Group and 6 were in the B Group in figure 7. In Group A, seven patients experienced treatment pauses during CT, while nine patients experienced them during RT. Five of them experienced RT and CT treatment interruptions. Two patients in Group B experienced treatment pauses during CT, whereas six patients experienced them during RT. During both RT and CT, two of these patients experienced treatment pauses. In our study, six patients experienced infections while undergoing treatment. Three patients had fungal infections, two had bacterial infections, and one had both. All of the other patients are in Group A, whereas the patient who had both infections is in Group B. 10 study participants experienced readmissions to the hospital for a variety of reasons, such as anemia necessitating blood transfusions, nausea or vomiting necessitating supportive care, etc. Nine of these

participants were in the A Group, while one was in the B Group.

Side effects such as nausea, anorexia, are commonly observed in patients on chemotherapy treatment. In our study 55% individuals failed to achieve planned nutritional treatment due to such side effects. It is supported by the earlier studies of Capuano where 53% individuals had difficulties to uptake planned nutrition [24]. Malnutrition results from a reduction in nutrient intake caused by the patient's interest in food, meal preparation, and eating abilities [25]. We found 30% individuals with malnourished conditions that had low survival rate as well.

Patients need to evaluate in a daily basis by medical expertise and required nutritional supplement should be provided as early as possible. In case of head and neck cancer, nursing nutrition intervention is the better choice for the patients to co-operate with the effective treatment [26]. Dietary counselling is essential in order to avoid unnecessary weight loss while patients are on treatment [27]. Megestrol acetate is useful to regain the food intake to balance appropriate weight [28].

Nutrition counselling has been documented to enhance clinical endpoints and nutritional intake for the patients undergoing chemo radiation therapy [24,29] or radiation alone [30,31]. In four studies nutrition counselling by a dietician was superior to general dietary recommendations from a nurse or no counselling at all [30–33]. Nutrition may enhance long-term outcomes in colorectal cancer [34]. Two studies of patients undergoing chemo radiotherapy have demonstrated that weight loss decreased in patients receiving nutritional intervention compared with no intervention, while

compliant patients lost less weight than non-compliant patients [24,29].

Patients with higher pre-therapy weight loss seemed to experience more benefit from nutritional counselling as they lost less weight post-therapy compared to patients who showed no pre-therapy weight loss. This contradicts earlier reports that the weight loss usually persists while undergoing cancer treatment [24]. We observed 33% weight loss among individuals on treatment. Our study also showed that a more severe treatment-induced nausea and anorexia led to a much higher rate of weight loss for the overweight patients whose BMI >25 kg/m². At the end, their muscle mass and strength are kept clinically superior to those of patients with less than 25. This might explain why weight reduction due to treatment is not related to survival. Obese patients lost greater amounts of weight, a phenomenon that

has been noted for Stage III-IV head and neck and cancer patients in general. Patients with higher BMI values before therapy seem to have experienced more nausea and anorexia, and thus lost more weight [35,36]. Overweight patients showed higher energy needs due to slowed gastric emptying as a result of inadequate nutrition and such energy need is difficult to match during chemotherapy. Low BMIs might also have meant less undesirable side effects of chemotherapy [37].

Therefore, follow-up nutritional guidance by expertise are necessary for the patients treated with chemotherapy, especially while dealing with side effects of treatment in a third week after taking chemo. Also, weight management is major factor, putting maximum efforts to prevent reduction of muscle mass (Table 2).

Table 2: Outcome of the study

Parameters	Outcome
Post-Treatment Side Effects	Chemotherapy commonly induces nausea and anorexia.
Nutritional Challenges	55% of patients failed planned nutritional treatment due to side effects; 30% were malnourished with low survival rates.
Impact of Nutritional Counselling	Demonstrated to improve weight management and clinical outcomes; dietician-guided counselling is superior to general dietary advice or no counselling.
Pre-Therapy Weight Loss	Patients with prior weight loss experienced less weight reduction during therapy compared to those with no pre-therapy weight loss.
Overweight Patients	Higher BMI patients (>25 kg/m ²) experienced greater nausea and weight loss due to increased energy needs and slower gastric emptying during chemotherapy.
Obese vs. Low BMI Patients	Obese patients lost more weight but maintained better muscle mass; low BMI patients reported fewer chemotherapy side effects.
Immune function	Enhances immune function, reflected by improved white blood cell counts and immune biomarkers.
Survival outcome	Indirect improvement in survival outcomes through better tolerance and completion of treatment.

Conclusion

The study underscores the importance of structured nutritional support during chemoradiation for head and neck cancers, highlighting its positive impact on patient outcomes. While changes in hemoglobin, albumin, and weight were not statistically significant, the support helped patients better tolerate treatment-related toxicities like mucositis and skin reactions. These results advocate for the integration of organized nutritional care into oncology protocols to improve recovery, treatment adherence, and quality of life.

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